

English Subject Teachers' Perceptions and Strategies in Managing Large Classes: A Case Study of Nepal

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Abstract

This research paper entitled "English Subject Teachers' Perceptions and Strategies in Managing Large Classes (A Case Study of Nepal)" was conducted with the objectives of finding out English subject teachers' perceptions on managing large ELT classes and to find out the current strategies adopted by the teachers. For the research purpose, fifteen English subject teachers were selected from the five different higher secondary schools of Nepalgunj, Banke district, Nepal by using purposive, non-random sampling procedure. In addition, I observed of three classes of each teacher was done. I employed two types of tools; questionnaire and observation checklist for collecting data. The finding shows that most of the English subject teachers are well-aware to manage the large classes and they have to adopt elective approach while dealing in a large class of Nepal.

Keywords: large class, teacher's perception, ELT, teaching strategy, quality of teaching

1. Introduction

This study is based on English subject teachers' perceptions and strategies in managing large Classes. As in ELT classes in Nepal, teachers, have to adopt different strategies to manage the large classes for teaching.

1.1 Background of the Study

English is an international language as well as lingua franca. It is the language of power, prestige, properties and life style in the present scenario. English is also the language of employment practice, classroom pedagogy, learning goal, norms and models for teaching, commerce, travel and tours, innovation, media, administration, communication, information technology, human rights, e-media, arts, culture, literature and so on. For that reason, the craze of English language teaching and learning is rising in the present era.

English language has been used for understanding and creating the literature of foreign countries. Awasthi (2009, p. 3) says, "English is widely used also medium of communication for different purposes, not only the vehicle of writing or reading British, American literature." It means English language is used in different countries for different purposes i.e., not only for basic purposes, communication but also language for business and official. The demand for English language by non-native speakers has been increased in most of the countries where English is used as a second or foreign language. In this regard, another writer Harmer (2007, p. 21) states, "The speaker of world English is perhaps capable of dealing with wider range of English varieties than someone stuck with the native-speakers' attitudes and competence." The users of English are multiplying day-to-day and English language is now a language of common mass, not only a few elites. So, the identity of English language is not only 'English' but also 'Englishes'. Regarding this, Richards and Rogers, (2005 p. 1) posits, "Language teaching in the twentieth century was characterized by frequent change and innovation by the development of sometimes competing language teaching ideologies." The assumption of language teaching and learning has been shifted the existing roles of both the teachers and students. Today, education is perceived as fundamental rights of human beings. It fosters all the potentialities and holistic development of an individual that language teacher put each learner at the central point of teaching process. Such as classroom management and organization of activities are in favor of their needs, abilities and emotions.

Thus, teaching learning process emphasizes the right to education and also the right to quality of education for all. In this regard, Bhattarai and Gautam (2008) state that:

In Nepal, it is used to be the exclusively British English prescribed for the ELT curricula, however, due to the globalizing world through trade, technology, media and relation. Nepal, for the last decades has experienced transition in the use of English language in terms of variety. This situation has demanded to adopt the more flexible approach in the selection and use of English language each and eclectic manner rather than being prescriptive. (p. 13)

This quote clarifies that English language is the need of globalization. To keep the changing concept, ELT planners and practitioners of Nepal have recently introduced and used more eclectic, interdisciplinary, multidisciplinary methods and materials. From methodological perspectives, we are in the post-methods era. To be the context sensitive, self-innovative for adaption of newer and nobler methods, which are suitable for the particular context, would work for better solution of ELT problems.

To ensure the quality of education and provide equal learning opportunities for each individual, there are some new emerging issues and approaches such as inclusive education, learner friendly environment, gender sensitive education, globalization, need based education and life-based education. Therefore, to ensure the learning opportunity, the teacher should focus such specific issues that need to be addressed when teaching in large classes. Thus, teachers' perception towards managing large classes and their current strategies to adopt suitable materials and all-round ability to cope such problems is becoming the main concern of present study in Nepal. Large classes are the major obstacles to ensure quality education. However, managing large classes in ELT classroom is not an easy job. It requires quite a great effort to a teacher to play various roles, ideas, abilities and consciousness. Therefore, the ELT modern era is based on hybridization of various methods and techniques to create own unique third method and technique in a dynamic way. It need not to be a standard method to follow in all cases, it needs to be self-innovative.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Teaching English language in Nepal in Higher Secondary schools varies due to the class size, managing mixed ability, monolingual, bilingual and multilingual status. To manage large classes and adopt appropriate methods and technique in a classroom is certainly a difficult task. However, it is not impossible one. The problem is that we assume learning occurs in proportion to class size. The smaller class, the more students learn. However, research shows that class size does not automatically correlate with students learning but the quality of teaching. Students in large class can learn just as well as in small ones. What counts is not the size of the class but the quality of the teaching. Evidence shows that students place more emphasis on the quality of teaching than the size of class. The teacher can apply several things for this.

1.3 Objectives of Study

The study had following objectives:

1. To discover the English teachers' perceptions on managing large classes.
2. To see the current strategies adopted by English teachers for managing large classes.
3. To provide some pedagogical implications.

1.4 Research Questions

To understand English subject teachers' perceptions and strategies in managing large classes, the following are research questions are raised:

1. What are the English subject teachers' opinions towards managing large classes?
2. Are teachers aware of managing large classes?
3. What are current practices to manage large English class?

1.5 Significance of the Study

English language teachers have many challenges for teaching students such as diverse and mass classes', multi-abilities together as well. Having students with difference in language proficiency is one of the problems that teachers face. This research is useful for English language teachers who are facing the problem of large classes at higher secondary level in Nepal. It was equally useful for those who are directly and indirectly involve in designing curriculum, preparing materials and writing textbook.

1.6 Delimitations of Study

This study had following delimitations;

- The study was delimited to five higher secondary level schools of Nepalgunj, Banke, Nepal.
- Only fifteen English teachers are selected for the study of higher secondary level.
- This was delimited for managing large classes only.
- Only three classes of each teacher were observed.
- Questionnaire and observations list are the only tools for data collection.

2. Conceptual framework and review of literature

2.1 Concept of the Large Classes

Large class means a class having a large number of students. Teaching English in large classes is one of the major challenges in ELT setting. The majority of classroom consists of multilevel groups where, students have different needs, learning styles, age, attitude towards the target language, learning experience, motivational orientation etc. English language classes greatly vary in size not only because of teaching aids but also because of the learning context and medium of instructions. Harmer says, (2007, p.122) says, "Everything depends on the particular education system that a teacher is working in. That is why if you ask a teacher what a 'large-classes' is they might answer, 20, 40, 60 or 80 even as many as 100 (and sometimes even more)." A large class has no 'exact size' usually it measures in terms of the number of students per teacher.

Thus, a large class has many students and a multilevel class has students of different levels. According to UNESCO, (2006, p. 1),

Actually, a large has no 'exact size' usually it is measured in terms of number of students per teacher (student teacher ratio). In some countries 25 to 30 students per one teacher is consider large, while in other countries this is seen to be normal or even quite small. From the teachers' perspectives, a class is 'large' whenever it feels large while a class of more than fifty students is usually considered a large class to those of you who normally teach twenty-five students or fewer students' class of 35 can be large and overwhelming. "Classes of 40 or more students: indeed, sometimes considerably more than 40 are the norm for the majority of English teachers and learners in the world but this reality has received relatively little attention in 'mainstream' ELT discourse." (Retrieved by pre-publication version of a paper in Pattison, T. (ed.) 2012, IATEFL, 2011).

Therefore, large class is a relative concept which measures the dependency of the diversity of various components such as linguistic status, learning context, class size, mixed abilities, methodologies, resources, physical facilities and teacher ability to tackle the problem and handle the classes.

2.1.1 Large Classes in the Context of Nepal

According to Education Regulation of Nepal (2059) maximum number of students in a single class at secondary level depends on the geographical regional criteria. Such as, in Terai or valley the maximum number of students is up to fifty. Similarly, in the hilly region, the maximum number of students is up to forty-five and in the mountainous region, the maximum number of students in a single class is up to forty. Similarly, School Sector Reform Plan (SSRP, 2066 - 2072) declared that the maximum number of students in a single class is decreasing at the secondary level. Such as, in the beginning phase of this program, the existing number of students in a single class was up to forty-two whereas, twenty-five numbers of students in a single class are the ultimate goal of this programme, which is going to be achieve by the year 2015 A.D. That is to say, 25 numbers of students in a single class at secondary level is the desirable number of students for a teacher to handle the classroom properly.

2.1.2 Problems of Managing Large Classes

Classroom management is the major issue to achieve the expected learning behavior of the students through the interaction. A good teacher should manage his/her classroom in such a way that it should be easier and enjoyable for both students and teacher, and fosters the inspiration of individual learners

It is difficult to enumerate all the problems to manage the large ELT classes because small-class teaching as a norm and teaching in large classes as a problem. Those problems, which are related to manage the large ELT classes, cannot ignore at any time. Some of the major problems to managing large according to Ur (2000) classes as below:

- Discipline
- Individual Attention to the Students
- Teachers Discomfort
- The Provision of Teaching Materials
- Teaching Learning Process
- Correcting Written Assignment
- Interest
- Lack of the Understanding

According to Nolasco and Arthur, (1991) state the problems of a group of teachers felt they encounter when they try to introduce pair and group work into a large class which are as follows:

- a) Discipline is a problem.
- b) The students are not interested when the teacher talks about which they are unfamiliar with.
- c) There are too many physical-constraints, such as rows of desks which are screwed to the floor.
- d) It is virtually impossible to provide the necessary duplicated materials.
- e) Students prefer grammar and exam practice.
- f) The school administration and teachers in the other classes do not like the noise when all the students talk at the other classes so not like the noise when all the students talk at the same time.
- g) Students will not use English when they are putting into pairs and groups.
- h) Although group work and pair work are the key technique to cope with various problems in large ELT classes, there are a number of problems that we have to encounter while applying their techniques.

2.1.3 Challenges and Opportunities of Large Classes

"Teaching large classes is a challenge, but it can also offer many opportunities for you to improve your teaching and to make it more enjoyable and rewarding for you and your students" – UNESCO, (2006, p. 2). Therefore, large class always offers both, challenges and opportunities simultaneously.

2.1.3.1 Challenges of Large Classes

Each learner is a unique individual. Equal treatment of all learners according to their individuality is not an easy job. In the context of large classes, teachers generally feel greater challenges rather smaller once.

There are two types of challenges:

- Physical challenges such as chair, desk, and benches.
- Psychological challenges such as motivation, intelligence, attitudes, aptitudes, learning strategies, learning abilities, co-operation, mother tongue interference, socio-cultural background and socio-political condition.

2.1.3.2 Opportunities of Large Classes

It is certainly true that teaching large classes have some specific opportunities. Large ELT classes setting the opportunity to improve teacher organizational and managerial skills as their work to create and organize their classroom into comfortable, welcoming learning environment and managed the many students within it. It offers the opportunities to improve the teacher interpersonal skills as he/she tries different ways to know each student as unique through their work in class or their lives outside of it. It also gives the opportunities to improve teachers teaching and presentation skills. It also provides the opportunities to learn each other's through collaboration and co-operation. It also provides the opportunities to bring varieties in the classroom.

2.1.3.3 Strategies for Managing Large Classes

Various methodologies have suggested different teaching tips and strategies for coping with challenges in large classes. We should say that lecturing, acting and joking should be offer in large classes. UNESCO (2006) some practical strategy for teaching for large classes as follows:

- a) Creating a well-managed classroom community, so that teacher and students are ready to learn in a comfortable, physical and psycho-social environment.
- b) Teaching in large classes includes planning lessons and choosing effective, alternative to the standard lecture format.
- c) Evaluating and teaching a large class, so that the teacher can provide the good opportunities for students to show what they are learning and teacher can reflect on their own teaching practices.

2.2 Review of Literature

To manage large classes, the teacher should make certain teaching strategies because the teacher is central agent to manipulate the instructions, planning and getting students prepared for learning through various techniques and strategies. For this, I have gone through some previous literature, which is as follows:

Neupane (2007) conducted a research entitled "A Study on Language Learning in Large Context in the Nepalese Context." The main objective of the study was to find out the problems faced by students and explore the ideas emerged from teachers' perspectives in teaching large classes. Thani (2008) carried out her research entitled "The Role of Classroom Management." Her study intended to identify and analyze the physical resources of the secondary English classrooms. Chamlagain (2009) carried out a research entitled "Characteristics of a Good English Language Teachers." The objective was to find out students' expectation of good teacher. Bashyal (2010) carried out a

research on the same field entitled "Strategies of Classroom Management Used by Secondary Level English Teacher." The main objective of this research was to identify the common strategies used by secondary level English teacher for classroom management.

The researches mentioned above are related to classroom management, it is not studied to try to find out the views of teacher's on managing large classes teachers' perceptions and practices in the present context at higher secondary level. Therefore, I conducted the research as a new attempt in the exploration of above-mentioned new area.

3. Methods and Procedures of the Study

This chapter deals with the methodology adopt to fulfill the objectives of the study. This includes design and methods of the study, population sample and sampling strategies, study areas, data collection tools, techniques data collection procedures and analysis of interpretation and data.

3.1 Design and Methods of the Study

The research design of this study was the survey research. The broad area of survey research encompasses any measurement procedures that involve asking questions of respondent.

3.2 Population Sample and Sampling Strategies

The population of this study was all the higher secondary level English teachers of Nepalgunj, Banke, Nepal. Out of them, the sample of the study included 15 teachers from different higher secondary schools in Banke district. The selection was done through purposive non-random sampling procedure. Following the same procedure, fifteen English teachers from five different higher secondary level schools representing at least three teachers from each of the schools were taken as sample.

3.3 Study Areas/Field

The research areas of the study were five higher secondary level schools of Nepalgunj, Banke district of Nepal.

3.4 Data Collection Tools and Techniques

I used only two tools for gathering required information viz. questionnaire and observation checklist. In this regard, I used both close-ended and open-ended questions in the questionnaire. Finally, I observed the classroom of the respondents with the help of checklist.

3.5 Data Collection Procedures

I collected the data from the primary sources by administering the questionnaire.

4. Analysis and Interpretation of the Data

The collected data were transcribed, coded, analyzed, interpreted and then presented descriptively using appropriate statistical tools, diagrams and tables.

4.1 Analysis and Interpretation of the Result

After collecting the data from purposive non- randomly selected 15 teachers of Nepalgunj, Banke, I analyzed and interpreted those data which are collected from the primary sources. The main objective of this study was to find out strategies adopted by English subject teacher to manage large classes. The data collected from the informants are based on the set of questionnaires prepared for higher secondary level English subject teacher of Banke district and class observation. Open-ended and close-ended questions were provided to the sampled teachers in order to collect their views. The views expressed by the teacher towards the large size ELT classes and the things found in classroom observation are presented, analyzed and interpreted here in this chapter. Finally, the summary of the findings is also included.

A set of questions were provided to the respondents containing close ended and open-ended questions respectively. In order to draw the teachers' perceptions a set of questionnaires (Mostly closed-ended questions) with three alternatives viz: Agree, undecided and disagree; and open-ended question. The percentage is the main base for data analysis. While analyzing the data the total number of responses of each question and item was analyzed, tabulated or shown by using tables. Open- ended questions were asked to take the subjective responses from the informants.

4.2 Managing Large Class: Analysis and Interpretation of Teachers' Responses

The main aim of the statement was to find out whether the teachers are aware for managing large class. The responses obtained from the respondents are separately presented the following tables:

The statement was 'All learners are a unique in nature so we should manage the classroom to address the needs and interests of each learner.' The responses obtained from the respondents are systematically tabulated the following table.

Table No. 1: Manage the Classroom to Address the Needs and Interests of Each Learner

Agree		Undecided		Disagree	
No of teacher	Percent	No of teacher	Percent	No of Teacher	Percent
14	93.5	1	6.5	0	0

The table above shows, 93.5 percent of the total respondents is agreed with the statement, 6.5 percent marked undecided and none of them disagreed with the statement. The responses indicate that the teachers are well-aware to manage the large classes.

4.2.1 Problems for Managing Large Class: Analysis and Interpretation of Teacher's Responses

The main aim of the statement is to find out the practical problems that a teacher faces while dealing in a large class. The obtained responses are separately tabulated the following table:

The statement regarding this area was 'Students of different language (proficiency) level can successfully be taught together that the teacher is capable of adapting various techniques. The obtained responses are tabulated the following table.

Table No. 2: Teacher Capable of Adapting Various Techniques

Agree		Undecided		Disagree	
No of teacher	Percent	No of teacher	Percent	No of Teacher	Percent
9	60	3	20	3	20

The above table shows 60 percent of total respondents agreed, 20 percent marked undecided and 20 percent disagreed with the statement. According to obtained data it can be said that the majority of teachers are accepted that the need of capable and qualified teacher for ensure the quality of teaching in a large class.

4.2.2 Challenges and Opportunities of a Large Class: Analysis and Interpretation of the Teacher's Responses

The main aim of the statement was to find out the teachers' ability, whether they are aware to utilized the challenges as the opportunities. The responses obtained from the respondents are separately presented as below: A statement in this area was 'A teacher faces many challenges and opportunities while dealing within a large class. The responses obtained from the respondents are tabulated the following table.

Table No. 3: Many Challenges and Opportunities while Dealing Within a Large Class

Agree		Undecided		Disagree	
No of teacher	Percent	No of teacher	Percent	No of Teacher	Percent
13	87	1	7	1	7

The above table shows, 87 percent of total respondents agreed with the statement, rest of them 7 percent marked undecided and disagree with the statement. According to data obtained it can be said that the majority of the teachers are aware to utilize the challenges as opportunities in a large class.

4.2.3 Strategies Coping with the Problems: Analysis and Interpretation of Teachers' Responses

The main aim of this statement was to find out classroom strategies adopt by teachers while dealing within a large class. The statement and the responses obtained from the respondents are presented. A statement in this area was 'I always devise different level of exercises for different groups of students in the same class'. The respondents obtained to this statement are tabulated in the following table:

Table No. 4: Different Groups of Students in the Same Class

Agree		Undecided		Disagree	
No of teacher	Percent	No of teacher	Percent	No of Teacher	Percent
2	13.5	3	20	10	66.5

The table above shows, the total number of respondents 13.5 percent agreed, 20 percent marked undecided and 66.5 percent of them disagreed with the statement. According to obtained data, it can be analyzed that most of the teachers are not design the task according to the levels of the students in a large class.

Another statement was 'I often organize group work and pair works in the classroom'. The responses obtained to this statement are tabulated in the following table.

Table No. 5: Group Work and Pair Work in the Classroom

Agree		Undecided		Disagree	
No of teacher	Percent	No of teacher	Percent	No of Teacher	Percent
8	55.5	3	20	4	26.5

The above table shows, 55.5 percent respondents agree, 20 percent undecided and 26.5 percent marked disagreed with the statement: Since majority of the respondents showed their agreement with the statement, it can be concluded that most of the teachers organized group and pair work in a large class.

The next statement was 'What counts is not the size of the class but the quality of teaching'. The responses obtained to this statement are tabulated in the following table:

Table No. 6: Size of the Class but the Quality of Teaching

Agree		Undecided		Disagree	
No of teacher	Percent	No of teacher	Percent	No of Teacher	Percent
13	86	0	0	2	14

As indicated in the above table, out of total fifteen respondents, 86 percent agreed, none of them undecided and 14 percent marked disagreed with the statement. The data indicate that the majority of the teachers are accepted the quality of the teaching, not the size of the class.

4.2.4 Analysis of Teachers Responses on Managing Large Classes

The Physical management of the desks and benches also related to, arrangement of desks and benches, setting condition of the whole class, movement of the teachers between these arrangements. Therefore, it is an important strategy to determine the teaching and learning quality in a large class. The data obtained through the class observation of teachers are tabulated to this strategy as the table below:

Table No. 7: Physical Management of the Large Classes

Components	Orderly row		Horse shoes		Circle		Solowork		Separate table		Total	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No	%	No.	%	No	%
Arrangement of desk and benches	45	100									45	100
Ways of management between these arrangement			15	34	25	56	5	12			45	100

The table above shows, the management of desks and benches of the large class were orderly row. No one of the class was seen other conditions used as horse shoes, circle, solowork and separate table. The way of movement between these arrangements were found the majority of the average. According to obtained data it can be analyzed that most of the setting conditions of the large classes were orderly rows. The way of movement between these arrangements were average in rank that is not satisfactory for providing the learning opportunities for all learners in the large classes.

4.2.5 Way of Encouraging Students Participation

The analysis of the strategy 'way of encouraging student's participation', the motivate students towards learning and develop the ownership of their own learning is the most important factor in learning process. It helps to make all students engage to do at least something. The data obtained through class observation to this strategy are tabulated in the table below:

Table No. 8: Way of Encouraging Students Participation

Components	Excellent		Good		Average		Below the average		Poor		Total	
	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%
Read and write individually	2	4.5	15	33.5	23	55.5	8	8.5			45	100
Use of Library/ self-access material			15	33.5	25	55.5	10	22.5			45	100
Get them produce their own work			20	44.5	25	55.5					45	100
Ownership in learning			10	22.5	25	55.5	10	22.5			45	100

From the above table, it was found that the teachers used the strategy of encouraging students' participation as the balanced way, likewise to give the opportunities to the students for read and write individually used the self-access materials get them produce their own work and provided that feedback to them if necessary. The majority of obtained data rate were good and average however ownership development in learning strategy was not as good, as it to be.

4.2.6 Analysis and interpretation of Open-ended Questions

This section consists of one question. The main aim of the question is to find out the classrooms' problems if the teachers have faced difficulty one hand and the other hand to find out the actual classroom strategies if the teachers did not face any difficulty to handle the large class.

The teachers who have to face difficulty to handle the large class were required to mention the classroom problems. According to their responses the classroom problems that the teachers faced in ELT large classes are thematically presented as below:

- Maintaining the discipline
- Motivating for all students
- Monitoring problem
- Interaction problem
- Controlling noise
- Providing feedback
- To check written homework
- To prepare teaching materials
- To design the task
- To maintain the time
- To divide the group
- To avoid the misunderstanding
- Narrow down the gap between teachers and students

5. Summary of Findings

From the analysis and interpretation of the information obtained. The following major findings have been drawn.

- All the higher secondary level English teachers (i.e., 100%) are well aware to manage the large ELT classes. They are also aware of the fact that, managing large class goes beyond the physical management, psychological management, socio-cultural and ability management aspects of the learners.
- The teachers are aware of the fact that in a large class there might students having different language proficiency. However, significance teachers (i.e., 46.5%) do not devise levels of the activities for dressing needs, abilities of the students. To teach all the students at the same level as if they do not vary in their language proficiency (level).
- It was found that most of the teachers (i.e., 80%) are well recognized the large class is rich verities of human resources.
- It was found that a large class is rich variety in human resources. Therefore, it is always beneficial to divide the groups and get them interaction with the students. However, majority of the teachers (i.e., 60%) do not divide the groups of the students while teaching in large class.
- It was found that collaborative learning is instrumental in solving the problems in a large class. However, less than half of the teachers (i.e., 46.5%) do not encourage the students to learn with collaboration.
- It was found that large class poses different challenges and opportunities to the teachers. For most of the teachers (i.e., 87%), it is very difficult to decide what kind of instruction task, and materials is appropriate for all the students.
- It was found that most of the teachers (i.e., 56.5%) aware to utilized the challenges of the large class as the opportunities to improve their teaching skills.
- It was found that only few teachers (i.e., 55.5%) organized groups and pair works in a large class.
- It was found that many teachers (i.e., 60%) do not distribute the responsibilities in the class to the students for managing the large class.
- It was found that most of the teachers (i.e., 75%) do not encourage the participation of the students in learning. Therefore, low participation of the students lacks of the ownership of their own learning.

- It was found that teacher is in favor of to be creative, innovative and context sensitive to adopt the best methods and techniques to suit their teaching styles and characteristics of their students. However, most of them (i.e., 75%) unable to adopt the best techniques and methods rather they took it as it is.

6. Conclusion

By employing the two tools; questionnaire and observation checklist; and analyzing data, the researcher comes to the following conclusion regarding the teachers' views on managing large classes and current strategies they have to adopt in the class room.

Firstly, the physical management of the large classes likewise, arrangement of desk and benches, way of moving these arrangements, or setting conduction of the students was not in favor of learners sensitive. Secondly, the ways of arranging desk and benches were orderly rows which makes difficult to conduct group work, pair work collaboration in learning and provide the feedback to the student in group-wise or an individually for the teachers. Thirdly, they are also aware the fact that ELT large classes are as common as in the society. Therefore, a teacher should manage the class to address the needs, interest and ability of each learner. In addition, it is possible to make large class beneficial for all the students if the teacher is capable to design, various tasks, to the students. Moreover, the teachers are aware to utilize the teaching aids as one of the effective tools for instructing the students in a large class. Lastly, the teachers were not found as practical as they responded in the questionnaire forms. There was a group between theory and practice in a great deal.

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